

THE CONTENT OF THE PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS DIRECTED TO THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE COMPETENCE IN THE LESSONS OF SPECIALIST SCIENCES.

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Abstract: This thesis describes the creation of a changing environment in the process of developing teacher-student relations and creative competence. This article outlines a critical element of teaching in the specialist disciplines to support innovation and innovation.

Key words: expertise, creative, approach, learner, critic, organization, interactive, competence, situation, idea, opinion.

"Education as the main factor ensuring sustainable development" was recognized, and in the international concept of education until 2030 adopted by UNESCO, "Creating the opportunity to receive quality education throughout life" was accepted as an urgent task. The implementation of achievements aimed at improving the creative competence of future teachers in the educational system is the basis for the development of effective mechanisms for the training of highly qualified specialists, the adaptation of the assessment of the quality of education to international standards, and the achievement of high results in the modernization of the educational system. In particular, by improving the technologies of increasing the creative competence of the future technology education teacher, it will be the basis for creating the third renaissance's semantic foundation based on a creative approach to social existence and pedagogical processes. Pedagogical skills are very important in the content of the pedagogical process aimed at forming the creative competence of the future technology education teacher, which includes pedagogical creativity, the ability to solve educational situations and problems, pedagogical technology and includes the formation of qualities such as having an understanding of professional competence and creativity in innovative education.

One of the important issues is the formation of the professional competence of future technology teachers through specialized classes, as well as the education of the psychophysiology of students in the study of specialized subjects. In particular, paying special attention to the fact that teacher-student cooperation is one of the important factors affecting the methods and means of

developing the creative abilities of elementary school students is one of the topical issues of specialization and specialty sciences. It is known that the educational process has a two-way character and consists of equal relations between the teacher and students. It is necessary to properly organize the teacher education process leading this process, and it includes an important pedagogical process. The goal of the modern pedagogical education system is the general and is to achieve professional perfection. Any pedagogic profession is a complex and exciting process, so this profession, no matter what field it belongs to, makes a lot of demands on the future technology teacher. The goal of all areas of education is to educate a well-rounded person. But in this regard, in educational institutions, the sciences belonging to the aesthetic category - technology, music, fine and applied arts, literature and their interrelation play a key role. In particular, technology training in educational institutions, technology teachers should also have special knowledge, skills and qualifications, pedagogical skills and pedagogical skills.

Formation of creative competence of students in classes of specialized subjects is carried out on the basis of pedagogical process, conscious approach to students, development of their thoughts and creativity. This process includes the following:

The goal of the lesson is to inspire students to explore their own ideas, solve problems, and create innovations. The goals include defining an approach that fosters innovation and an educational environment that embraces innovation and creativity.

Teacher's roles and responsibilities: The teacher is very important in the development of students' creativity. They should organize the teaching process, inspire students to solve new problems, express their thoughts and guide them with creative approaches.

Conducting the educational process in an interactive state: In the process of forming creative competence, educational exercises and lessons should be interactive. This creates opportunities for students to express their ideas, master problems and support new creations.

Creation of new situations: Lessons should allow students to create new situations. These situations can be spent through problem solving, creating projects, conducting one's own work, creative exercises and other methods.

Management of concepts and ideas: It is necessary to increase the concepts and ideas related to students' expression of their thoughts and creative

approaches. They can support students' understanding and give them an opportunity to express their thoughts during the teaching process.

Critique and Evaluation: In the process of developing creativity, it is important for students to critically review and evaluate their ideas, projects, and creations. This helps them to update themselves, review their mistakes and develop their own skills.

Teamwork: Another important part of building creative competence is collective work among students. They need to exchange ideas with each other and create innovations. This allows them to share ideas from all sides and elevate their ideas to develop their creativity.

These contents are important to help students develop their creativity and self-mastery in specialized subjects. These changes will help students to master, create new innovations and reach the modern stages of specialization.

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